

Social Media Influence on Senior High Students' Spending Behavior for a Financial Management Plan

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Purpose: This paper focuses on the rising influence of social media on senior high school students' financial behaviour and uses the case study of a Manila student subjected to social expectations, attitude in spending, and perceived control. Social media is viewed as a new learning opportunity about finance, yet it tends to nurture consumerist tendencies associated with impulsive buying. Therefore, the research gap in the existing studies aims at detailing mechanisms by which social media impacts students' spending.

Study design/methodology/approach: A descriptive-correlational design was used, with responses obtained from 308 senior high school students through structured questionnaires. This allowed for assessing the correlations between social media influence, students' financial attitudes, subjective norms, perceived control, and spending behaviour patterns.

Findings: Key findings depict a good correlation between students' exposure to social media and their spending behaviour, which would articulate how digital platforms influence financial attitudes and decision-making. Integrating educational finance management into school curricula would support students in learning to think critically and responsibly about their finances. However, this cross-sectional study limits generalisation and calls for the agenda of longitudinal research in this area.

Originality/value: This paper contributes to the existing literature based on particular mechanisms about the impact of social media on student spending behaviour, especially within the context of Manila. It indicates the practical value of infusing financial education into school programs, promoting media literacy and financial responsibility in students to foster independence and long-term fiscal awareness.

Introduction

One of the most significant influences on the financial behaviours of youth worldwide is social media use. In this regard, the Philippines ranks first in internet use and engagement with social media (Kurešepi, 2021). Students tend to see lifestyle content on social media applications such as Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok, which encourages them to adopt consumerist attitudes. They can easily be influenced to waste their money, which may give way to myths about money management.

International researchers have established that social media pushes youth into the throngs of impulsive buying through selective advertising and peer influence. For instance, Gao et al. (2023) state how social media sites stimulate social comparison, thus leading one to indulge in compulsive buying behaviours. Likewise, Lajnef (2023) has concluded ways by which teenagers' choice of spending is influenced by influencers of social media pushing them more into the clutches of the consumerist order. Filipino senior high school students with weak

financial literacy are exposed to such influences and tend to impulsive spending and bad budgeting (Rodriguez et al., 2024).

This study investigates the impact of social media on the spending behaviour of senior high school students in Manila, serving as a case analysis reflective of broader trends. By examining how social media shapes financial attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control, the research aims to inform a financial management plan that helps students navigate social media's influence and make responsible financial decisions.

Research Question

The following questions to assess the influence of social media on the spending behaviour of senior high school students:

1. How does social media influence the spending behaviour of senior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Attitudes
 - 1.2. Subjective Norms
 - 1.3. Perceived Behavioral Control
2. What is the spending behaviour of the senior high school?
3. Is there a significant relationship between social media influence and the spending behaviour of senior high students?
4. What is the proposed financial management plan for senior high students based on the findings?

Hypothesis

HO: There is a significant relationship between social media exposure and the spending behaviour of senior high students.

Review of Relevant Literature

Social Media Influence

Social media has become an extremely influential tool in making financial decisions because it is a readily available gateway to financial information and also increases communication between users (Subramanian & Prerana, 2021). Recently, it has dominated spending and investment decisions among the youth. Ferah and Sumer (2023) claim that social media advances financial literacy by increasing access to information, creating peer-to-peer discussions, and presenting various investment opportunities. YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook are now learning platforms like quick tips on investing in stocks, where young adults share insights about different investment options that appeal to them, and such insights shape the financial decisions they make (Subramanian & Prerana, 2021). This trend shows how social media evolved from being a mere networking site to becoming an influential tool in shaping users' awareness and trends in investment.

Social media has its disadvantages, though. Prolonged exposure to carefully crafted content makes them believe that wealth is an issue of how much they spend, thus making adolescents adopt consumerist habits that encourage overspending. According to Lin (2023), it increases spending behaviours among teenagers and makes them have unhealthy attitudes about money. This is enhanced with attractive advertisements and convenience through increased buying

interest and facilitated decisions by factors of attentiveness, engagement, and information exchange (Budiyanto et al., 2022). Influence towards consumers and investment decision-making on social media remains a potent and frequent habit-forming attribute between millennials and Gen Z populations, especially towards expensive and impactful habits (Hasanudin, 2023). The platforms continue to shape financial behaviours, and it becomes necessary to understand the impact on spending habits to develop suitable financial literacy initiatives.

Spending Behavior

Spending behaviour can be quite different and very decisive, including a student's financial literacy, parent's income, and demographics determining what students will likely spend (Sandrasegaran & Rambeli, 2023). Spending behaviour varies by education and gender, and an apparent difference in the age of the individual spending the money reflects a gender-wise difference in spending behaviours by males and females (Bugheanu & Străchinaru, 2020). Personal costs such as beauty products, study needs, telecommunications, clothes, and health products will be the most identifiable, thus reflecting individual needs and, at the same time, the kind of faculty influence that affects these expenditure decisions as more decisive for young children. The two studies demonstrate an interesting student spending profile intersection of demographic and academic variables.

Moreover, students usually have typical spending habits at a more general financial level due to dependency on the type of income source and their savings. The usual allocation for students on necessities like education, transportation, food, clothes, and entertainment suggests what happens to be the most significant, everyday expense items and where all their money comes from (Raval, 2023). Studies also indicate that students' changing spending habits usually lower the savings rate as the ease of accessing money through the Internet bank facility may facilitate more spending (Sharmila, 2019). The overall financial culture has thus undergone a radical change, and there is much emphasis on studying the spending within the students' community to better promote financial discipline and prudence.

The Relationship between Social Media Influence and Spending Behavior of Senior High Students

Social media appears to have become a defining aspect of how teenagers understand and manage money, including those in senior high. Lin (2023) notes that constant exposure to social media content leads to money illusions and increases spending propensities since it encourages higher consumerist mindsets despite their financial realities. The spending behaviour of the youth is highly influenced by marketing strategies on these platforms, such as high advertisement frequency, trending fashion endorsements, influencer promotions, and branded content, which creates a pattern of consumption driven by external cues rather than personal financial planning (Johan et al., 2022). This is, obviously, significantly influencing teenage school-going since a proper knowledge of handling money is developed, or lacks at this age, which such teenagers find themselves within.

Besides, these social media websites are quite engrossing towards influencing young minds towards getting highly influenced by what friends around them are purchasing or buying products for because these spaces, social media are found as areas of constructing societal-approved consumption standards for one and all by youths around the world, (Beri & Kumari, 2022). This has been proven to enhance consumer preferences that conform to perceived social expectations for young users between 22 and 25 years of age, a trend that also applies to the younger cohorts who want to emulate the same consumption models (Erokhina & Fedorov, 2022). Thus, the more senior high school students are immersed in social media and its advertisements promoting such engagement, the more likely they are to adopt spending behaviours based on their desire to be socially desirable and up-to-date. These students have become the new face of online business. There is a need to understand this dynamic to address the financial management needs of such young consumers moulded by such strong influences through social media.

The Financial Management Plan for Senior High Students

Developing a financial management plan is crucial for the senior high school student as he faces financial responsibilities. Hence, schools should equip graduate students with effective personal financial planning skills. According to Rodriguez et al. (2024), students' financial management should involve their academic lifespan, focusing on developing practical financial skills. A structured, student-centred financial management plan includes seven key stages: assessing one's financial position, setting specific financial goals, creating a financial strategy, maintaining simple financial records, budgeting effectively, handling credit issues, and regularly reviewing finances. These stages are designed to support students in developing responsible spending habits and financial planning skills that will prepare them for future financial independence (Santoso & Binawat, 2023).

It also points out that when added to the curriculum, personal finance education can give students tools that help them manage finances in an organised manner, including how to budget, manage debts, save, and even invest (Sewell & Rogers, 2022). Triana and Ibrohim (2022) emphasise that a proper financial management approach for students should include the following: management, income, budgeting, education, and planning factors to bring about financial literacy. The financial management plans make students think of education as an investment in human capital, thereby taking a constructive attitude towards the costs incurred from education and long-term financial goals (Andreeva et al., 2020). At its foundation, this approach is a sound method for enabling students to manage their finances and be informed of sustainable financial management decisions.

Literature Gaps and Suggestions for Future Research

The relevance of social media in current literature relates to its significant influence on the spending behaviour of youth. However, there are still some relevant gaps that remain and should be addressed in more research studies. Most such studies are cross-sectional, meaning they provide a snapshot rather than a deeper causal understanding of how exposure to such media

for an extended period ultimately affects financial habits over time. While it is perceived that social media influence international spending, comparative and cross-cultural studies are limited to date, and questions persist as to how these cultural norms are shaping influences. Such research rarely probes the depth of psychological mechanisms that can stimulate consumerist behaviour, which takes the form of social comparison, peer pressure, or emotional triggers.

While much is often recommended as a solution in financial literacy, few studies have been executed to gauge the effectiveness of any targeted education interventions to neutralise the negative influences that social media triggers in spending behaviour. Most existing studies omit a group of demographic variables: socioeconomic status, urban versus rural locations, and preference for channels of social media, which may significantly influence spending behaviour. Further longitudinal studies are warranted as the psychological analysis will be more intense, and more effective financial education programs will be evaluated. In contrast, more subtle demographic analyses will form a deeper understanding and wise management of social media's impact on youth spending.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behavior

This explains how the Theory of Planned Behavior model works, depicting how attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control all build up to help shape the behavioural intentions in actual behaviour. Positive financial attitudes will encourage students to budget and save on their behalf because of responsible money practices. The research studies by Azidzul et al. (2023) have proved the association between attitude and financial literacy and skills concerning an individual's expenditure and saving behaviour. The compulsion through friends and relatives makes students spend or save because they have a norm which pushes them to make appropriate money management decisions; at times, it is introduced through encouragement received via social media since seeing other members within the social group properly manage their finances.

Financial literacy enhances the degree of perceived control in performing the behaviour, especially by the accomplishment of financial skills, which, once attained, enhances confidence among students in the correct performance of financial tasks. Financial literacy enhances the

degree of perceived control in performing the behaviour, especially by accomplishing financial skills, which, once attained, enhances confidence among students in correctly performing financial tasks. The TPB postulates that favourable intentions to exhibit prudent financial behaviours, consistent with attitudes, norms, and perceived control, result in responsible financial management behaviour that bridges the gulf between intention and action. This understanding is crucial in developing a framework that implements specific interventions, such as financial literacy programs, that are tailored to empower these students to make informed decisions on their finances.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: IV-DV Paradigm

This conceptual framework presents how Social Media Influence affects the spending behaviour of high school students mediated by several mediating constructs based on the theory of planned behaviour. Social exposure through social media initiates attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, which define spending intention as preparedness and readiness to spend responsibly. This intention is an immediate precursor to spending behaviour, which may be ascertained from the observable students' financial actions, such as budgeting, buying habits, and impulse expenditures. The insight acquired regarding social media's effect on these psychological aspects informs the determination of how to shape the students' financial behaviour responsibly.

Methodology

Research Design

This research will use a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the association between social media influence, the independent variable, and spending behaviour, the dependent variable of the senior high school students. Through a cross-sectional approach, it will be possible to capture data at one point so that strength and direction can be determined without controlling or manipulating the variables (Nasrun, 2022). Although this method is enlightening, it is generally limited by its lack of generalisability because any findings will reflect the time they were collected. No longitudinal component exists in this study, which

forbids drawing causal conclusions or seeing changes over time. Future research could benefit from a longitudinal design that can track shifts in social media influence and spending behaviour to keep much of their developments in perspective with each other.

Participants

The population for this study is 1,537 senior high school students in a university located in Manila and coming from different strands. Using Slovin's formula for calculating the sample size, 308 respondents were selected to ensure an accurate representation that would give reliable insights into whether or not social media affects spending behaviour. The use of simple random sampling gives an equal chance to the students to participate and supports the generalisation of this study to students. However, the cross-sectional nature limits a more wide-ranging application. Longitudinal studies are needed for high generalisation.

Data Collection

The researcher developed this structured questionnaire to assess social media's influence on students' spending behaviour. Pilot testing was conducted before full deployment to establish the validity and reliability of the instrument in utilising Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR) and Cronbach's Alpha, which aims for an α value of ≥ 0.70 . It ensured suitability and internal consistency for data collection. While this process lends credibility to this research, the cross-sectional profile reveals an area where longitudinal follow-up is necessary to track changes that occur with time.

Statistical Tools

Descriptive statistics, such as mean, standard deviation and frequency distribution, have been used to provide a summary profile of exposure to social media and spending behaviour. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was also applied to determine the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the influence of social media and spending behaviour. Even though these tools are suitable for correlational analysis, they cannot also determine causation, confirming the added value of longitudinal research in further studies to monitor trends over long periods.

Results and Discussions

The Social Media Influence to Spending Behavior in terms of Attitude, Subjective Norms and Perceived Behavioral Control

Table 1. Social Media Influence

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
<i>Attitude towards Social Media Influence</i>				
1. I believe that social media provides valuable information on the latest trends and products.	308	0.68069	3.1104	Agree
2. Social media encourages me to spend on items I might not otherwise consider.	308	0.61051	3.3539	Agree
3. I feel that the advertisements I see on social media are trustworthy and relevant to my needs.	308	0.58450	3.3377	Agree

4. Seeing friends and influencers on social media with certain products makes me more interested in buying them.	308	0.61076	3.1558	Agree
5. Social media positively influences my purchasing decisions by helping me discover new products and brands.	308	0.69307	3.1071	Agree
AVERAGE	308		3.2130	AGREE
<i>Subjective Norms Towards Social Media Influence</i>				
1. My friends' opinions on social media influence my purchasing decisions.	308	0.59776	3.1916	Agree
2. I feel pressured to buy products that I see frequently endorsed on social media.	308	0.66488	3.1429	Agree
3. Seeing my peers share their purchases on social media makes me want to buy similar items.	308	0.68718	3.0097	Agree
4. I believe that buying popular products on social media helps me fit in with my social circle.	308	0.63634	3.1948	Agree
5. The brands and products endorsed by influencers I follow make me feel that these items are worth purchasing.	308	0.80077	2.7143	Agree
AVERAGE	308		3.0506	AGREE
<i>Perceived Behavioral Control Towards Social Media Influence</i>				
1. I feel in control of my spending decisions, even when influenced by social media content.	308	0.72124	3.1916	Agree
2. I am confident in my ability to resist impulsive purchases promoted on social media.	308	0.69672	3.3864	Strongly Agree
3. I can manage my spending effectively, regardless of what I see on social media.	308	0.75991	3.2110	Agree
4. I believe I have the self-discipline to limit my purchases, even if social media encourages me to buy more.	308	0.75376	3.2175	Agree
5. I find it easy to stick to my budget despite being exposed to attractive products on social media.	308	0.75116	3.1688	Agree
AVERAGE	308		3.2350	AGREE
<i>Legend: "1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree", "1.76-2.50 Disagree", "2.51-3.25 Agree", "3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree"</i>				

The descriptive statistics indicate that the respondents seem to concur quite well on influence regarding attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control as far as exercising an influence on social media on financial decisions, which is consistent with research that suggests social media does indeed have an impact on spending and investment behaviour among young adults. With mean scores in the "Agree" scale of ATTITUDE (3.2130), SUBJECTIVE NORMS (3.0506), and PBC (3.2351), the result, as Ferah and Sumer (2023) would describe, points toward the fact that social media supports a moderately positive attitude towards financial decisions and provides some sort of social expectation that individuals should engage with observed behaviours online. This openness to social media influence, probably fueled by the increasing availability of financial information and online peer discussions on YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook, makes social media a critical source of financial literacy. However, this influence also has potentially harmful effects because exposure over time to these edited contents and ads may foster consumerist attitudes that can promote overspending and impulsive buying in teenagers, as argued by Lin (2023) and Budiyo et al. (2022). This dual impact of social

media—both as a learning tool and as a driver of spending habits—calls for financial literacy initiatives that should be able to empower users to critically view social media content and make balanced financial decisions, eradicating the habit-forming influence of such platforms among millennials and Gen Z populations (Hasanudin, 2023).

The Spending Behavior of Senior High Students

Table 2. Spending Behavior

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. I am likely to buy products that I see recommended or advertised on social media.	308	.75623	2.9318	Agree
2. I plan to set aside money for items I discover through social media platforms.	308	.75376	3.2175	Agree
3. I often intend to purchase trending products that my friends or influencers showcase online.	308	.85069	2.7338	Agree
4. I feel inclined to increase my spending on items that are popular on social media.	308	.86048	2.6948	Agree
5. I am willing to spend more on brands and products that are frequently promoted by influencers I follow.	308	.86031	2.8312	Agree
AVERAGE	308		2.8818	Agree
<i>Legend: "1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree", "1.76-2.50 Disagree", "2.51-3.25 Agree", "3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree"</i>				

Table 2 Indicates that an average mean score of 2.88 falls within the "Agree" range for items related to spending behaviour inspired by recommendations, advertisements, and influencer promotions. This aligns with Sandrasegaran and Rambeli (2023), who established the existence of various factors that impact student spending behaviour, among which were students' financial literacy, family income, and family demographics. Considerable agreement with the above statements referring to the tendency to purchase trending or promoted products (means from 2.69 to 3.22) indicates that social media acts as a stimulus for purchase decisions, more especially in clothes, cosmetics, and other personal expenses - a sound aspect related to the spending habits concerning personal needs (Bugheanu & Străchinaru, 2020). The data also reflects how ease of access to social media and online financial tools can encourage impulsive spending, consistent with Sharmila's (2019) observation that digital banking facilities reduce saving rates among students. These findings highlight that social media's influence intersects with students' financial profiles and demographics, emphasising the need for financial education to promote prudent spending habits amidst social media's strong sway over consumer choices.

The Relationship Between Social Media Influence and Spending Behavior

Table 3. Pearson Correlations

		<i>p</i>	<i>Pearson's r</i>	<i>Decision on Ho</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCE	SPENDING BEHAVIOR	.000	.486	Reject the Ho	There is a significant relationship between Social Media Influence and Spending Behavior.

The data reveals a significant relationship between social media influence and spending behaviour among youth, as indicated by a Pearson's *r* value of 0.486 and a *p*-value of 0.000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and confirming a positive correlation between these variables. This result underscores Lin's (2023) observation that constant exposure to social media cultivates consumerist mindsets, encouraging spending patterns driven more by social cues and the allure of trending content than personal financial planning. Marketing strategies like high-frequency advertisements, influencer endorsements, and branded content, as noted by Johan et al. (2022), foster consumption habits in young users who may lack financial literacy. It also aligns with Erokhina and Fedorov's (2022) findings that young adults, particularly those in senior high school, are likely to adopt spending behaviours to fit social expectations, viewing consumption as a route to social acceptance.

These findings align with the global perspective. However, cultural-specific facts about Filipino students, under the thrust of local socioeconomic determinants (Rodriguez et al., 2024), show that some financial literacy programs would be appropriate. It will be through customised training that will balance the increased tendencies of consumers, which are produced by social media (Beri & Kumari, 2022). In general, this research reveals that financial education should ideally be incorporated to teach responsible expenditure among students due to strong influences from social media. Therefore, financial habits among the youth are shaped by social media, and it is within this context that there is an immediate need for financial education programs that can make them better thinkers and money managers amidst entrenched influences from the online.

The Financial Management Plan for Senior High School

Table 4. Financial Management Plan

<i>Area</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Strategies</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Person Involved</i>	<i>Outcome</i>
Financial Literacy	Improve understanding of financial concepts and planning	Conduct workshops on budgeting, saving, and responsible spending; integrate financial literacy modules into the curriculum	Quarterly	Finance Educator, Teachers	Students gain foundational knowledge of budgeting and financial planning

Social Media Awareness	Build awareness of social media's impact on spending	Host seminars that highlight social media's role in consumer behaviour; invite experts to discuss advertisement tactics and their effects	Biannually	Social Media Expert, Counsellors	Students become more aware of how social media influences their spending habits
Budgeting Skills	Enable students to create and manage a personal budget	Provide templates and guide students in developing monthly budgets; assign project-based learning for real-life budgeting exercises	Monthly	Teachers, Financial Coaches	Students learn practical budgeting skills and track their spending against their financial goals
Peer Influence Management	Reduce impulsive spending influenced by peers	Organise group discussions to foster critical thinking about peer pressure and social norms related to spending	Every Semester	Counsellors, Peer Leaders	Students develop self-control and awareness of the impact of peer pressure on spending behaviours.
Savings Motivation	Encourage regular saving habits	Set up a school savings program with small rewards for reaching savings milestones; promote savings goals	Ongoing	Teachers, Bank Representatives	Students establish savings routines, building a habit of setting aside money for future needs
Goal Setting	Help students set realistic financial goals	Introduce goal-setting exercises related to short-term (weekly) and long-term (monthly/annual) financial goals	Monthly	Teachers, Counsellors	Students learn to set, monitor, and adjust financial goals, fostering forward-thinking financial habits
Digital Financial Literacy	Teach safe online spending and banking practices	Provide sessions on secure online transactions, recognise online scams, and safely use digital wallets and banking apps.	Annually	IT Teachers, Bank Representatives	Students become savvy and secure in handling online transactions, reducing risks in online spending

Parental Involvement	Engage parents in financial literacy efforts	Hold workshops for parents to support financial lessons at home; send newsletters with updates on school financial literacy programs	Quarterly	Parents, Financial Educators	Parents reinforce financial principles taught at school, creating a supportive environment for learning
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This financial management plan for senior high school students aims to equip them with practical financial skills focusing on budgeting, savings, and social media awareness to prepare them for financial independence (Rodriguez et al., 2024). Structured into key objectives—improving financial literacy, managing peer influence, and fostering budgeting and savings habits—the plan aligns with the seven stages, including assessing financial positions, setting goals, budgeting, and reviewing finances (Santoso & Binawat, 2023). Through workshops, seminars, goal-setting exercises, and parental involvement, students gain hands-on experience managing and handling spending and setting financial goals, echoing Triana and Ibrohim's (2022) suggestion to incorporate income management, budgeting, and education into financial literacy efforts. Additionally, integrating personal finance into the curriculum, as suggested by Sewell & Rogers (2022), allows students to approach their education as an investment in human capital, fostering a constructive attitude toward financial planning and the costs associated with long-term financial goals (Andreeva et al., 2020). This plan is designed to empower students to make sustainable financial decisions and prepare them for a financially responsible future.

Conclusions

This research demonstrates the influence that social media has on the expenditure of senior high school students as set by the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). Moving through the TPB, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control are all considered to establish precisely what such attitudes bring about regarding intention and behaviour pupils take when choosing to consume. Student spending is framed within the TPB, refocusing emphasis on the consumerist pressures produced through social media. These results are more aligned with identifying the theoretical contribution through the use of TPB in aiding the comprehension of digital influences regarding financial behaviour.

Practically, the research enforces the need for financial education programs in schools' curricula. These programs should centre on enhancing financial literacy, emphasising self-regulation, and teaching pupils how to set responsible relationships with money despite the contagion influence of norms from peers and social media. With budgeting, saving, and strategic financial planning skills, such educational interventions can equip the transition to adulthood with indispensable fiscal prudence.

A future study may also explore more longitudinal designs to understand if sustained exposures through social media have time-related impacts on financial behaviour and how effective targeted financial education programs are. Further studies could also be expanded with respect to the cross-cultural spectrum, which has its own takes and nuances on both social and economic

factors playing into the influence of social media, therefore giving a much deeper understanding of worldwide trends in youth spending behaviour.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, here are the following recommendations for social media influence impacting the spending behaviour of the students:

1. Proper education needs to be provided to school-going children through media literacy and critical thinking sessions on how social media forms their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control of financial choices
2. Schools should conduct periodic reviews of students' spending behaviour and analyse such patterns so that the school authority can address cases of overspending and provide students with useful budgeting tools for common areas of spending.
3. Financial literacy programs should thoroughly educate students on the psychological and social motivations of expenditure, budgeting, and saving and on practices regarding impulsive buying resulting from social media.
4. School curricula must have a formal financial management plan, including goal setting, budgeting exercises, discussion of how social media influences them, proper Internet use to avoid unwanted purchases, and reinforcement from parents so that these students are constantly reminded at home.
5. Future research should examine how people spend their money and resources based on social media influence, even after a long period in which all age groups spend or do not spend more funds on the same services or goods. In this way, the financial habits of people within a time frame are being understood.

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